

THE ATTITUDE AND PERFORMANCE OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF A CHINESE SCHOOL IN MATHEMATICS TAUGHT IN MANDARIN AND ENGLISH

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The Attitude and Performance of Junior High School Students of a Chinese School in Mathematics Taught in Mandarin and English

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Abstract

This study delved into the comparison of students' performance and attitudes toward Mathematics in Junior High School when taught in English and Mandarin, aiming to discern the influence of language on student outcomes. By drawing upon Don Elger's Performance Theory and Daniel Katz's Functionalist Theory of Attitudes, the research explored how instructional language shapes student attitudes and performance in Mathematics. Utilizing a descriptive correlational analysis approach, data from structured questionnaires and academic grades were scrutinized using statistical methods such as t-tests, weighted mean, standard deviation, and the Pearson Product-Moment Coefficient of Correlation to unveil patterns and relationships between instructional language, attitude, and academic achievement in Mathematics. The findings revealed significant insights: (1) No significant difference was observed in the performance of students in Mathematics taught in English versus Mandarin; (2) Significant disparities emerged in the attitudes of students toward Mathematics when taught in English versus Mandarin; (3) Negligible and insignificant correlations were found between students' performance and attitude in Mathematics taught in Mandarin; and (4) Low but significant correlations were observed between students' performance and attitude in Mathematics taught in English. These findings underscored the pivotal role of attitude in academic performance, aligning with the Functionalist Theory of Attitudes, which posits that individuals seek to maximize rewards and minimize penalties in their environment. Furthermore, the results supported the Theory of Performance, suggesting that educators, regardless of the instructional language, should enhance teaching methodologies to enhance students' proficiency in Mathematics.

Keywords: *bilingual education, language of instruction, mathematics performance, student attitudes*

Introduction

Numerous studies have been conducted throughout the country to ascertain the state of Chinese education. Students enrolled in Chinese schools are primarily Filipino Malay people who have had no prior contact with the Chinese and have no base whatsoever (ICETSS, 2014). Since 1973 (the promulgation of the Philippine Constitution), the time spent in Chinese classes has changed. Due to the limited time allotted for Chinese education and the high rate of forgetting, Chinese teachers allot time, say 10 minutes, to review the previous session, resulting in significantly less time spent teaching the subject. This is because, rather than strictly adhering to the Chinese curriculum, courses tailored to Filipino students should be taught as well.

Language plays a crucial role in learning, especially in subjects like mathematics. The choice of language for instruction can significantly impact students' attitudes and performance in the subject. In this study, we aimed to explore the influence of language—specifically Mandarin and English—on the attitude and performance of students in mathematics. Understanding this influence can provide valuable insights for educators and policymakers to optimize the learning environment for bilingual students or learning mathematics in a language that is not their first language (Moschkovich et al., 2018). Mathematics is a compulsory subject in education and aims to develop logical, analytical, critical thinking, and creative thinking skills in students (Zhou Ying et al., 2020). However, many students have a low interest in mathematics because it is difficult to understand, and the teaching method is boring. The student's attitude toward mathematics is closely related to their learning achievement and is influenced by the teaching method and material.

Chinese students have consistently showcased exceptional mathematical skills, often surpassing peers from other nations in competitions like the International Mathematical Olympiad (IMO) and the China Girls Mathematical Olympiad (CGMO) (He et al., 2022). Zhang and Li (2017) attest to the historical dominance of Chinese students in these competitions, epitomizing their mathematical prowess (Zhao, 2020). For instance, China's top-ranking performance in the 2019 IMO underscores the nation's dedication to mathematical excellence (International Mathematical Olympiad, 2019). This competitive advantage underscores the need to investigate the language of instruction's impact on students' mathematical achievement and attitudes, particularly in bilingual settings like junior high schools in China. Understanding how instructional language influences student performance and attitudes can offer valuable insights for educators and policymakers to optimize mathematics education strategies, enhancing students' mathematical skills and confidence (Mazana et al., 2018).

Drawing upon Don Elger's Performance Theory and Daniel Katz's Functionalist Theory of Attitudes, this study aimed to explore how the language of instruction influences students' attitudes and performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the attitude and performance of students in mathematics taught in Mandarin and English for Grade 7 to

Grade 10 students. Specifically, this sought answers to the following:

1. What is the level of performance of the Grade 7, Grade 8, Grade 9, and Grade 10 students in Mathematics:
 - 1.1. with Mandarin as medium of instruction; and
 - 1.2. with English as medium of instruction?
2. Is there a significant difference between the performance of the Grades 7, 8, 9, and 10 students in Mathematics taught in Mandarin and English?
3. What is the attitude of the Grade 7, Grade 8, Grade 9, and Grade 10 students in Mathematics:
 - 3.1. with Mandarin as medium of instruction; and
 - 3.2. with English as medium of instruction?
4. Is there a significant difference between the attitude of the Grades 7, 8, 9, and 10 students in Mathematics taught in Mandarin and English?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the students' attitude towards Mathematics and their performance in the subject:
 - 5.1. with Mandarin as medium of instruction; and
 - 5.2. with English as medium of instruction?

Literature Review

Chinese Education

Chinese education boasts a rich legacy dating back to the 16th century B.C., initially reserved for the elite class and strongly influenced by Confucian teachings (Bahtilla & Xu, 2021). The Han Dynasty later ushered in public education, democratizing access to learning for commoners. In the Philippines, Chinese education found its roots in 1899 with the establishment of the Tong Se Academy in Binondo, funded by Chinese merchants, eventually paving the way for more Chinese schools nationwide, offering scholarships to poor students (Ho, Michael Wong, 2024).

These schools, exemplified by one institution dedicating substantial time to Chinese subjects, particularly Chinese Mathematics, have garnered a reputation for excellence in local, national, and international competitions. Their prowess in Mathematics presents a challenge for other institutions to match (American Mathematical Association of Two-Year Colleges, 2018). Despite similar curricula in both English and Mandarin, variations in students' academic performance exist. Thus, this study sought to delve into the differences and similarities in students' attitudes and performance toward Mathematics in both languages.

Filipino-Chinese schools in the Philippines have evolved, incorporating Standard Chinese (Mandarin) alongside a diverse array of subjects. These institutions typically adhere to the curriculum outlined by the Philippine Department of Education, emphasizing Chinese Grammar, Composition, and Mathematics as core subjects, while integrating subjects like Calligraphy, history, geography, and culture. While historically pivotal in fostering Chinese nationalism and cultural preservation, these schools have adapted to align with Filipino educational standards, welcoming students of all ethnicities. The transformation into Filipino Chinese schools in 1973 aimed to integrate with the national curriculum while preserving the Chinese language and culture, seen in the 207 Chinese schools across the Philippines, six of which are in Cebu, offering both the Department of Education's K to 12 Curriculum and the Chinese Curriculum (Ho, Michael Wong, 2024).

Factors Influencing Mathematics Learning

Numerous factors influence students' mathematics achievement, but there are limited studies that examine the influence of psychology on student mathematics achievement. Teachers' and parents' support, stress, and students' well-being all play a significant role in affecting mathematics achievement. Students' interest in learning was the most significant factor influencing their mathematics achievement (Wijaya et al., 2022). Additionally, self-efficacy, which is a student's belief in their ability to succeed, was found to be an important predictor of mathematics achievement. Other factors that influence student achievement include motivation, attitude, and learning styles.

Attitude is a learned predisposition involving cognitive, affective, and cognitive components. In Katz's Functionalist Theory of Attitudes, instrumental, knowledge, value-expressive, and ego-defensive functions are distinguished ("Attitude," n.d.). According to Festinger (1957) as mentioned in (McLeod, 2023), inconsistencies between actions and beliefs can lead to negative attitudes. ARCS Model of Motivational Design, motivation plays a major role in attitude formation, as it emphasizes attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction (ARCS Model of Motivational Design Theories, n.d.). Further, language presents notable challenges in mathematics learning, particularly in diverse linguistic contexts (Nahole & Haimbodi, 2022). To facilitate effective mathematical comprehension and application, language barriers must be addressed. Language can also be used to support mathematical reasoning and thinking (Wilkinson et al., 2018). It can be used to construct meaningful numerical representations and concepts. Further, language can help learners understand math more deeply by scaffolding learning.

Teacher Influence in Mathematics Learning

Teachers, pivotal in education reforms, directly impact students' attitudes and academic performance (Tang & Hu, 2022). Teachers

have roles in engaging students' intellect, developing mathematical understanding, stimulating problem-solving and reasoning, encouraging communication, and embodying Mathematics as an ongoing human activity, making teachers' inconsistency with students' learning styles can lead to negative attitudes (Ayuwanti et al., 2021). Besides, the language of instruction, as seen in various studies, significantly affects Mathematics performance, reinforcing the importance of educators understanding the linguistic needs of their students (Bermejo et al., 2021).

This study aimed to delve into the dynamics of students' attitudes and academic performance in Mathematics within the Chinese curriculum. The primary focus is on Grade 7 to Grade 10 students, evaluating their achievements and attitudes when Mathematics is taught in Mandarin and English. The objectives encompass a comprehensive analysis of performance levels, investigating potential differences based on the medium of instruction.

Language plays a crucial role in learning, especially in subjects like mathematics. The choice of language for instruction can significantly impact students' attitudes and performance in the subject. In this study, we aimed to explore the influence of language—specifically Mandarin and English—on the attitude and performance of students in mathematics. Understanding this influence can provide valuable insights for educators and policymakers to optimize the learning environment for bilingual students or learning mathematics in a language that is not their first language (Moschkovich et al., 2018). Mathematics is a compulsory subject in education and aims to develop logical, analytical, critical thinking, and creative thinking skills in students (Zhou Ying et al., 2020). However, many students have a low interest in mathematics because it is difficult to understand, and the teaching method is boring. The students' attitude towards mathematics is closely related to their learning achievement and is influenced by the teaching method and materials.

Theory of Performance

The Theory of Performance (ToP) proposed by Don Elger offers a comprehensive framework for understanding and enhancing individual and organizational performance. This theory delineates six foundational concepts that elucidate the nature of performance and mechanisms for its improvement. Central to ToP are three axioms: mindset, immersion in an enriching environment, and engagement in reflective practice, which are posited as essential for fostering effective performance enhancements.

ToP acknowledges the remarkable capabilities of humans to achieve extraordinary feats, ranging from liberating nations from colonial rule to pioneering space exploration. Within diverse learning contexts, ToP proves invaluable in elucidating the mechanisms underlying successful performance. At its core, performance entails the integration of skills and knowledge to yield valuable outcomes. Through iterative cycles of improvement, performance advances through successive levels, resulting in the attainment of superior results within compressed timeframes.

Moreover, ToP emphasizes the systemic nature of performance, highlighting the intricate interplay between various components within a system. The effectiveness of a system's performance hinges on the synergy and interactions among its constituent elements.

Integral to ToP is the concept of reflective practice, which entails deliberate actions aimed at extracting insights from experiences. This process involves observing performance, critically analyzing strengths and areas for improvement, and augmenting one's knowledge base to facilitate continuous growth and development.

The ToP framework shares commonalities with other constructs in the literature, such as Thomlinson's Parallel Curriculum and Bransford et al.'s model for effective teaching and learning. These parallels underscore the interconnectedness of various theoretical frameworks aimed at elucidating the intricacies of human performance and learning. By embracing the principles outlined in ToP, individuals and organizations can cultivate a conducive environment for fostering continuous improvement and achieving optimal performance outcomes.

Methodology

This research employed a descriptive method with a correlational analysis research design to investigate the relationship between students' attitudes and their performance in Mathematics. The study specifically focused on exploring these dynamics when Mathematics was taught using Mandarin and English as media of instruction.

The data for this study were collected through a structured questionnaire designed to assess students' attitudes toward Mathematics when taught in Mandarin and English. The 42-item questionnaire required participants to express their responses on a scale ranging from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree." Additionally, academic performance was measured by obtaining students' grades in Mathematics for both Mandarin and English.

This study's statistical treatment of data employed several tools to analyze and interpret the results. First, the t-test of two independent samples was used to determine if a significant difference exists between the performance and attitude of students in Mathematics with English and Mandarin as media of instruction.

The weighted mean was utilized to assess the significant difference in the performance of students in mathematics with English and Mandarin as the media of instruction. When investigating students' attitudes and performance in mathematics, using standard deviation can uncover patterns in the distribution of scores, identify outliers, and offer a more comprehensive understanding of the entire data

set. This approach can assist researchers in identifying groups of students with similar attitudes or academic achievements and pinpointing areas where intervention or support may be necessary. Lastly, the Pearson Product-Moment Coefficient of Correlation, denoted by 'r,' identified if there is a significant relationship between academic performance and the attitude of students.

Participants

The study included all Grade 7 to Grade 10 students enrolled in both the Chinese Curriculum and the K to 12 Curriculum. Of the total of 78 students enrolled in the High School Chinese Curriculum, 72 were found to be at the same grade level in both the Chinese and DepEd curricula. This comprised 20 students in Grade 7, 16 in Grade 8, 21 in Grade 9, and 15 in Grade 10. However, three students were excluded from the study, resulting in a sample size of 69 participants.

Results and Discussion

The study found that students' grades in Mathematics taught in Mandarin consistently exceeded the performance target of 75 across Grades 7 to 10. Specifically, students in Grade 7 ($M = 84.97$, $SD = 4.57$), Grade 8 ($M = 87.33$, $SD = 5.67$), Grade 9 ($M = 87.60$, $SD = 5.90$), and Grade 10 ($M = 89.33$, $SD = 5.00$) demonstrated significantly higher performance levels ($p = 0.0001$) than the established standard. This observation aligns with the emphasis on the rigorous Chinese curriculum, which includes Mandarin as the primary medium of instruction for subjects like Language, Literature, History, and Mathematics from the early grades onward (American Mathematical Association of Two-Year Colleges, 2018).

The historical legacy and reputation for excellence in Chinese education, may contribute to the elevated performance levels observed in this study. The integration of Mandarin into various subjects, coupled with a focus on Chinese Mathematics, likely fosters a strong foundation in mathematical concepts and skills among students (Ho, Michael Wong, 2024). Furthermore, the study supports the notion that language plays a crucial role in mathematics learning, as highlighted in the literature review. Despite the differences in the medium of instruction, students immersed in the Chinese curriculum exhibit robust performance, underscoring the effectiveness of Mandarin as a language of instruction in mathematics education.

Overall, the findings suggest that students' sustained exposure to Mandarin instruction within the Chinese curriculum contributes to their heightened performance in Mathematics, surpassing established standards. This underscores the importance of considering language as a determinant of academic achievement and emphasizes the potential benefits of bilingual education in fostering mathematical proficiency (Bermejo et al., 2021).

Table 1. *The Performance Level of the Respondents in Mathematics Taught in Mandarin*

Grade Level	n	Hypothetical Mean	Actual Mean	SD	Computed t	p - value	Qualitative Description
7	18	75	84.97	4.57	9.2558*	0.0001*	Above Average
8	15	75	87.33	5.67	8.4222*	0.0001*	Above Average
9	21	75	87.60	5.90	9.7865*	0.0001*	Above Average
10	15	75	89.33	5.00	11.1000*	0.0001*	Above Average

*Significant

The study also revealed that students' grades in Mathematics taught in English surpassed the performance target of 75 across Grades 7 to 10, as shown in Table 2. Specifically, Grade 7 students achieved an average score of 88.61 ($SD = 5.55$), Grade 8 students achieved an average score of 87.50 ($SD = 0.26$), Grade 9 students achieved an average score of 85.98 ($SD = 6.74$), and Grade 10 students achieved an average score of 86.37 ($SD = 6.37$), all with a significant p-value of 0.0001.

The literature review supports this outcome by emphasizing the transferability of skills and techniques acquired in Mathematics taught in Mandarin to Mathematics taught in English. The rigorous Chinese curriculum, as discussed, incorporates diverse mathematical techniques and problem-solving strategies, which students found beneficial when applying them to Mathematics taught in English. Through focused group discussions, students expressed how their proficiency in Mathematics taught in Mandarin enhanced their performance in English-language Mathematics, enabling them to approach problems more efficiently and effectively.

Moreover, the competitive advantage gained by students who have exposure to both Mandarin and English instruction in Mathematics is highlighted. By leveraging the techniques learned in Mathematics taught in Mandarin, students reported saving time and achieving success in local, national, and international Mathematics competitions. This underscores the practical utility of bilingual education in Mathematics and its positive impact on students' academic achievement and extracurricular accomplishments (Moschkovich et al., 2018).

Table 2. *The Performance Level of the Respondents in Mathematics taught in English*

Grade Level	n	Hypothetical Mean	Actual Mean	SD	Computed t	p - value	Qualitative Description
7	18	75	88.61	5.55	10.4040*	0.0001*	Above Average
8	15	75	87.50	0.26	186.2011*	0.0001*	Above Average
9	21	75	85.98	6.74	7.4654*	0.0001*	Above Average
10	15	75	86.37	6.37	6.9130*	0.0001*	Above Average

*Significant

In Table 3, an analysis across all grade levels revealed a significant difference in the performance of Grade 7 students in Mathematics taught in Mandarin compared to Mathematics taught in English. Specifically, Grade 7 students exhibited significantly higher performance in Mathematics taught in English than in Mandarin. This finding aligns with the literature review, which suggests that the choice of language for instruction can impact students' attitudes and performance in mathematics. While both languages cover related topics, the easier nature of Grade 7 Mathematics taught in English, often focused on reviewing basic algebraic concepts, may contribute to the observed difference in performance.

However, when considering the overall performance of all respondents, no significant difference was found between their grades in English and Mandarin. This suggests that, on average, students performed above average in both languages. The literature review supports this notion by emphasizing the potential benefits of having two Mathematics subjects, as students may gain mastery of the lessons through exposure to related topics in both languages. This is in line with Jerome Bruner's theory of instruction, which posits that guiding learners through a sequence of statements and restatements of a problem or body of knowledge enhances their ability to grasp, transform, and transfer what they are learning. Thus, the interconnectedness of topics across languages may facilitate a deeper understanding and retention of mathematical concepts among students.

Table 3. Differences in Mathematics Performance of the Respondents Using Mandarin and English as Media of Instruction

Grade Level	n	Medium of Instruction				Test Statistics	
		Mandarin		English		Computed t	p-value
		x	SD	x	SD		
7	18	84.97	4.57	88.61	5.55	2.147*	0.039012*
8	15	87.33	5.67	87.50	0.26	0.116 ns	0.908481 ns
9	21	87.60	5.90	85.98	6.74	0.829 ns	0.412024 ns
10	15	89.33	5.00	86.37	6.37	1.416 ns	0.167804 ns
Overall	69	87.23	5.54	87.05	6.44	0.147 ns	0.883573 ns

ns = not significant, * significant

As depicted in Table 4, the study revealed a positive attitude among respondents toward Mathematics taught in both English and Mandarin. Across all grade levels (Grades 7, 8, 9, and 10), students demonstrated high levels of positivity towards Mathematics taught in Mandarin, as indicated by respective mean scores of 2.96, 2.92, 2.73, and 2.65, with standard deviations ranging from 0.28 to 0.41.

Despite perceiving Mathematics taught in Mandarin as challenging, students expressed enthusiasm for acquiring additional techniques from their teachers, which differed from those taught in English. This highlights the value students place on diverse learning experiences and the potential benefits of exposure to different instructional approaches. Moreover, students' positive attitudes towards Mathematics taught in Mandarin suggest an appreciation for the unique insights and strategies it offers, which they believe will ultimately provide them with a competitive advantage.

Overall, the study underscores the significance of attitude in shaping students' learning experiences and outcomes in Mathematics. By acknowledging the importance of attitude and embracing diverse instructional methods, educators can create a supportive learning environment that fosters students' engagement and success in mathematics education.

Table 4. Attitude of the Respondents in Mathematics Using Mandarin and English as Media of Instruction

Grade Level	n	Mandarin			English		
		x	SD	QD*	x	SD	QD*
7	18	2.96	0.28	Positive	2.95	0.29	Positive
8	15	2.92	0.37	Positive	3.14	0.28	Positive
9	21	2.73	0.41	Positive	3.07	0.31	Positive
10	15	2.65	0.30	Positive	2.85	0.26	Positive
Total	69	2.80	0.37	Positive	3.01	0.31	Positive

*QD - Qualitative Description

Table 5 indicates that among Grades 7, 8, and 10 students, there were no significant differences in attitudes toward Mathematics when taught in Mandarin versus English. However, Grade 9 students exhibited a more favorable attitude towards Mathematics taught in English compared to Mandarin.

While students generally showed positive attitudes towards Mathematics taught in Mandarin, Grade 9 students' preference for English instruction may stem from concerns over the teaching approach. The literature suggests that instructional strategies involving memorization, common in Mandarin instruction, may lead to disengagement and reluctance among students, particularly if they perceive such methods as less effective or engaging.

The reported reluctance of some students to participate in Mandarin Mathematics classes due to the emphasis on memorization aligns with the literature's discussion on the importance of instructional relevance and student engagement. Educators should consider incorporating varied instructional approaches that cater to students' diverse learning preferences and foster active participation. This

may involve integrating more interactive and problem-solving-oriented activities to enhance students' motivation and enjoyment of Mathematics, regardless of the language of instruction.

Table 5. Differences in Attitude of Grades 7, 8, 9, and 10 Toward Mathematics with Mandarin and English as Media of Instruction

Grade Level	n	Medium of Instruction				Test Statistics	
		Mandarin		English		Computed t	p-value
		x	SD	x	SD		
7	18	2.96	0.28	2.95	0.29	0.105 ns	0.9170 ns
8	15	2.92	0.37	3.14	0.28	1.836 ns	0.0770 ns
9	21	2.73	0.41	3.07	0.31	3.031 *	0.0043 *
10	15	2.65	0.30	2.85	0.26	1.951 ns	0.0611 ns
Overall	69	2.80	0.37	3.01	0.31	3.614 *	0.0004

ns = not significant, * significant

The findings from Table 6 reveal a noteworthy correlation between Grade 9 students' attitudes and academic performance in Mathematics within the Mandarin curriculum ($r = 0.5177$, $p = 0.0117$), signifying a substantial and significant relationship. This result aligns with existing literature highlighting the intricate interplay between students' attitudes and academic outcomes in Mathematics. Wijaya et al. (2022) emphasize the significance of students' interest in learning as a predictor of Mathematics achievement, while Nahole & Haimbodi (2022) underscore the impact of language barriers on students' academic performance.

However, when considering the overall performance and attitude of all students across different grade levels, no significant correlation was observed. This suggests that, while attitude may influence academic performance for Grade 9 students specifically, it may not have a consistent impact across all grade levels. This finding resonates with the literature's discussion on the complexities of language instruction in Mathematics. Despite students' positive attitudes towards the subject, language-related challenges may hinder the translation of attitudes into academic success, particularly in bilingual instructional settings (Nahole & Haimbodi, 2022).

The discrepancy between attitude and performance in Mathematics taught in Mandarin underscores the need for targeted language support and instructional strategies. Educators should consider implementing scaffolded approaches and language integration techniques to address students' linguistic needs, as suggested by Wilkinson et al. (2018). By providing additional support and fostering a conducive learning environment, educators can enhance students' comprehension and application of mathematical concepts, ultimately bridging the gap between attitude and performance in Mathematics within bilingual contexts.

Table 6. The Correlation between the Attitude and Performance of the students in Mathematics taught in Mandarin

Grade Level	n	Variables	X	SD	Test Statistics		
					Computed r	Degree of Association	p-value
7	18	Grade	84.97	4.57	0.1056	negligible	0.6767 ns
		Attitude	2.96	0.28			
8	15	Grade	87.33	5.65	0.0374	low/slight	0.8947 ns
		Attitude	2.92	0.37			
9	21	Grade	87.60	5.90	0.5117	marked/ substantial	0.0177 *
		Attitude	2.73	0.41			
10	15	Grade	89.33	5.00	0.2296	low/slight	0.4104 ns
		Attitude	2.65	0.30			
overall	69	Grade	87.23	5.54	0.0725	negligible	0.5538 ns
		Attitude	2.80	0.37			

As gleaned in Table 7, Grades 7 and 10 showed no significant correlation between their attitude and performance in Mathematics taught in English. In Grade 8, there was a marked substantial but not significant correlation. Only the Grade 9 students showed a substantial significant correlation between the attitude and performance of the students in Mathematics taught in English. Students who exhibited a positive attitude towards Mathematics performed well in the subject. So, the attitude of Grade 9 students is a predictor of their performance in Mathematics. As a whole, there was a slight but significant correlation between the students' attitude and their performance in Mathematics.

The positive attitude of students in Mathematics taught in Mandarin and English supports the Functionalist Theory (Katz, 1960). The respondents may have labeled Mathematics as a mental abuse through their scribbles on their Math notebooks and memes being posted on social media, yet they still consider the fact that if they get low grades in both subjects, they might be reprimanded and given some penalties such as no cell phones and Wi-Fi for a week or two. People tend to develop a positive attitude toward maximizing rewards and minimizing penalties (Katz, 1960). One thing the students cannot deny about learning Mathematics in Mandarin is that, despite the difficulty of the subject and the language, it gives them much confidence (ARCS Model of Motivational Design) which would take part in the formation of the attitude of the learners. The ARCS Model of Motivational Design (Keller, 1987) articulates four steps for promoting and sustaining motivation in the learning process: Attention, Relevance, Confidence, and Satisfaction.

Table 7. *The Correlation between the Attitude and Performance of the Students in Mathematics taught in English*

Grade Level	n	Variables	X	SD	Test Statistics		
					Computed r	Degree of Association	p- value
7	18	Grade	88.61	5.55	0.2297	low/slight	0.3592 ns
		Attitude	2.95	0.29			
8	15	Grade	87.50	0.26	0.4291	marked/ substantial	0.1105 ns
		Attitude	3.14	0.28			
9	21	Grade	85.98	6.74	0.4609	marked/ substantial	0.0355 *
		Attitude	3.07	0.31			
10	15	Grade	86.37	6.37	0.1125	negligible	0.6898 ns
		Attitude	2.85	0.26			
overall	69	Grade	87.08	6.44	0.2630	low/ slight	0.0290 *
		Attitude	3.01	0.31			

ns= not significant, * significant

Students might not be as attentive to Mathematics taught in Mandarin as in English because of the level of difficulty of the medium being used by the teachers, but their attitude is positive because most of them considered Mathematics taught in both English and Mandarin as cultural, practical, profitable - for it teaches them accuracy and techniques giving them an edge among others. Some of the respondents stated how the alumni managed to make mathematics easier in college because of the techniques taught to them not just by the English teachers but also in Mandarin. The respondents see themselves as a beneficiary of the joined forces of Mathematics taught in English and Mandarin.

Conclusion

The study used the correlational research design to determine the relationship between the attitude and performance of students in Mathematics taught in Mandarin and English of Grade 7, Grade 8, Grade 9, and Grade 10 students. The 42-item questionnaire was used to determine the attitude of students. Their grades determine the Academic Performance of the students. 69 respondents participated in this study.

The study's findings illuminate the significant positive attitude displayed by students toward Mathematics when taught in both Mandarin and English, offering valuable insights into the dynamics of language influence on the learning experience. This affirmation resonates strongly with the Acculturation Model proposed by John Schumann, suggesting that learners naturally aspire to assimilate into the lifestyle and behaviors of the target language group for practical reasons. The recognition of this inclination emphasizes the importance of considering cultural and linguistic factors when designing educational strategies.

Furthermore, the study highlights a nuanced relationship between attitude and academic performance, contingent upon the medium of instruction. This aligns with the tenets of the Functionalist Theory of Attitude presented by Daniel Katz, asserting that individuals are motivated to maximize rewards in their environment while minimizing penalties. In Mathematics Education, the varying impact of attitude on academic performance underscores the complexity of the learning process and the multifaceted interplay between language, attitude, and scholastic achievement.

These findings underscore the need for educators and curriculum developers to appreciate the intricate connections between language, attitude, and academic outcomes. By acknowledging and leveraging students' positive attitudes in both Mandarin and English contexts, educational institutions can enhance the effectiveness of their instructional methods and foster a conducive learning environment.

Implication

Based on the findings of this study, practical steps can be taken to enhance mathematics education in Chinese curriculum schools. A first recommendation is to encourage Mandarin-speaking math teachers to diversify their teaching methods by incorporating positive reinforcement and innovative techniques. To ensure a comprehensive approach to math skill development, it is also recommended that Chinese and English curriculum administrators collaborate. It is also recommended that teachers move away from traditional rote learning in favor of fostering conceptual understanding in their students. Students from both the Mandarin and English curricula would benefit from collaborative efforts between Mandarin and English instructors. Guidance counselors need to play a pivotal role in cultivating students' positive attitudes toward math. Lastly, the study highlights the need for future research to encompass a wider range of Chinese schools in the Philippines for more robust insights.

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